

METHODS FOR EFFECTIVE USE OF PROVERBS IN THE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: This topic explores ways to effectively use proverbs in the educational process, especially in the native language, literature, and extracurricular activities. Proverbs serve as a means of enriching students' oral and written speech, deepening moral and educational concepts, instilling national values, and enlivening topics. It also highlights methods for developing students' thinking, analysis, and discussion skills through the use of proverbs in the lesson. The topic considers the criteria for selecting proverbs in the lesson, their combination with interactive methods, and the possibilities of using them in the integration of different subjects.

Key words and phrases: Proverbs, lesson process, speech culture, educational significance, oral creativity, revitalization of the topic, national values, activity of the skill of expressing opinions, interactive methods, extracurricular materials, integration (interdisciplinary connection), examples and analysis, moral education, approach through problematic questions.

One of the largest and most ancient genres of folk oral art is proverbs. Proverbs are a treasury of wisdom of the people, short, meaningful, figurative expressions that express their socio-educational views. They are of great importance in enriching the means of expression in the language, forming a culture of thinking, observation and speech in students. Therefore, a unique approach is required in the process of teaching proverbs in general secondary schools. Proverbs are one of the highest examples of folk oral art, embodying the life experience, social relations and moral criteria of the people.

They attract the attention of students with their short, concise and figurative expression, expand the scope of their thinking. Therefore, using them in the lesson increases the effectiveness of education. At the beginning of the lesson, a proverb is said that is appropriate to the topic and students are asked to explain its meaning.

This attracts them to the topic. If the topic of the lesson is "labor" – Proverbs: "He who labors is satisfied." You can increase your vocabulary or strengthen grammatical devices through the words in proverbs. Proverbs: "Do good, jump into the river." Exercise: It can also be used to analyze verb tenses or

find synonyms/antonyms. In the lesson, a problematic question is asked based on the proverb and a debate is organized. Proverb: "You can drive a snake out of its nest with your tongue." The proverb is given as a topic and an assignment is given to write an essay or story. Proverb: "A friend is known at the beginning." Each group is given a proverb, which they act out or illustrate by drawing. Knowledge is reinforced through tasks to fill in the end of the proverbs or correct the incorrect ones. "He who has not run much, ... (find the correct one)." Through proverbs, students get acquainted with the values and traditions of the Uzbek people. A proverb appropriate to the topic is told and students are asked to explain it. This method attracts students to the topic and increases their activity. "He who has read knows, he who has not read does." When explaining a new topic, it is easy to provide understanding through proverbs. Through it, the viability of the topic is proven. Knowledge is strengthened by organizing tests, explanatory notes, dramatic scenes, and exercises through proverbs. Students learn to express their opinions when discussing proverbs. By interpreting proverbs and searching for information about them, students learn to work with information. Each proverb reflects the mentality, values, and philosophy of life of the people.

By analyzing them, students are educated in the spirit of respect for national and universal values. Amaliy usullar va interaktiv topshiriqlar Practical methods and interactive tasks Method Content Sample Analysis Grammatical or semantic analysis of the proverb "Good intentions are half a state." – what word groups are involved? Continuation of the proverb The beginning is given, the reader finds the ending "He did not run much, ... (he ran a little)." Staging Prepare a scene suitable for the proverb "A friend is known at first." – short dialogue Find a proverb based on a picture A picture is shown, a proverb is said to match it Picture of a threshing floor – "Whoever works hard, his hand is high." Written task Write a story based on a proverb "You can drive a snake out of its nest with your tongue." – write a life story Proverbs can also be used in other subjects:

History: "The father is gone - the son is the inheritance." - a conversation about historical figures. Biology: "Water is the source of life." - a discussion about the importance of water. Literature: Describing the character of characters in works with proverbs. Proverbs instill in children concepts such as national values, moral standards, patriotism, hard work, honesty. For example, proverbs such as "He who serves the people will be the head of the people," "Honesty is the greatest wealth" cultivate positive qualities in students. Proverbs

are used in lessons as a language and literature tool. Proverbs are widely used in Uzbek language and literature lessons for the following purposes: Increasing vocabulary; Explaining phraseological expressions; Working with text; Understanding and analyzing the meaning of phrases.

Example: In the 5th grade native language textbook, within the framework of the topic “Proverbs are a treasure trove of wisdom”, students work on proverbs such as “If you bow your head, trouble will return”, “Do good, even if it does not return, it will return”, explain their meaning, and give real-life examples. Use in integrated lessons; Proverbs are used not only in native language and literature, but also in lessons integrated with subjects such as history, geography, and biology. For example, in a history lesson, “The lesson of the past is the way forward” Historical memory and lesson concepts are discussed based on the proverb. Integration with interactive methods; The following methods are effective in working with proverbs: “Finish the proverb” - the student tells part of the proverb, another student continues; “Understand the proverb” - an example from a real life situation is given to the given proverb; “Find the proverb” - the task of finding a proverb suitable for a specific situation.

These methods serve the student's independent thinking, quick response, and increase the richness of speech. Different approaches in primary and higher grades In primary grades, proverbs are used mainly as a means of developing oral speech and teaching language, while in higher grades they are used as a means of forming analytical thinking and artistic thinking. Finding proverbs suitable for the actions of the heroes of the work in literature lessons increases artistic perception in students. Proverbs are one of the ancient and richest forms of folk oral creativity. They express the life of society, human experience, and moral and normative views. Proverbs are an expression of the experience and wisdom of the people accumulated over the centuries.

They provide the richness of the language, imagery and expressiveness of speech. This article discusses the scope of application of proverbs, their functional tasks and methodological features. Proverbs are mainly didactic in nature and perform educational, instructive, meaningful advice. They are actively used in the following areas: In oral speech, proverbs are often used as evidence, as a means of reinforcing thought or deepening the content. The proverb “Do good, do not hold back” calls on a person to be kind. In literary texts, proverbs are used to create an artistic image, reveal the character of the hero, and give a folk tone. Abdulla Qodiriy made effective use of proverbs such as “If there is a homeland, there will be a people” in his novel “Bygone Days”.

Proverbs serve as an important tool in teaching moral and normative concepts in the upbringing of preschool and school-age children. Proverbs are widely used in television programs, radio programs, articles and interviews to emphasize an idea or give a folk spirit. The proverb “A peaceful homeland, a peaceful people” is often used in political speeches. It is also widely used on the Internet and social networks. In today's digital age, proverbs are widely used in memes, statuses and short posts due to their brevity and completeness of content.

Conciseness - short, but deeply meaningful. Rhythmicity - has a rhymed and melodic structure. Imagery - often relies on metaphor, irony and other artistic means Grouping proverbs according to their themes (labor, friendship, morality, motherland, etc.). Linguistic-cultural approach: Studying the mentality and values of the people through proverbs. Analyzing Uzbek proverbs in comparison with those of other peoples. For example: In Uzbek, “Tilingni tiy – boshing omon” is similar to it in English, “Loose lips sink ships”. Proverbs constitute the artistic and aesthetic wealth of the language as a reflection of folk wisdom. They are formed on the basis of life experience, increase the expressiveness of speech, and have a moral and educational impact.

Each sphere - literature, education, mass media, and modern technologies - uses proverbs according to its needs. The use of proverbs in the lesson process serves as an important tool for increasing the activity of students, forming independent thinking in them, enriching oral and written speech, and educating respect for national values. It forms their aesthetic taste, spiritual world, and national consciousness. In this regard, the teacher's creativity and methodological approach are of decisive importance. Providing examples of folk wisdom in each lesson makes the lesson interesting, effective, and effective. Each teacher must form the effective use of proverbs as his or her own pedagogical skill, in accordance with his or her subject and class

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